

Title: Making great AI for consumer products

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INTRODUCTION:

Using artificial intelligence (AI) in consumer products is the new hot trend; except, it's not new at all. Come learn from a product management view of what makes a good AI system and what are the key success criteria to using it in any consumer facing product.

AIM:

To clarify common misconceptions about what AI can do as well as provide examples of how to best use of AI in products.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Juston has been on the leading edge of AI and consumer electronics for over a decade while working with some of the biggest names in consumer electronics (Apple and Samsung) and AI (Andrew Ng).

RESULTS:

n/a

CONCLUSIONS:

n/a

KEYWORDS:

n/a

BIOGRAPHY:

Juston Johnson has worked all over the globe in pursuit of developing the best consumer products. He started with an AI focus in Computer Science at Stanford University under Andrew Ng while also completing a second degree in Religion Studies. Then after a few years in consulting, he went on to business school at the Tuck School of Business at Dartmouth with a focus on global business management. That lead him to take on a number of international roles that include strategy, business development, R&D and product management at tech companies such as Samsung, Beats by Dre, Apple, and an AI focused startup called [i.am+](#). His current role is dedicated to bringing voice-first contextual, conversational AI to hardware consumer electronics. In his free time, Juston teaches capoeira (a Brazilian martial art) and trains in many other martial art forms. He also likes to play video games and work on maintaining the various languages he has learned over the years.